

e-ISSN: 2582-2993

Volume 09 Issue 02 May-
Aug 2026

*Corresponding Author:
Pranit Kumbhar,
Student, DACOE, Karad,
India

Submission Date: Feb 25,
2026

Copyright Received Date:
Mar 01, 2026

JalRakshak: Real Time Water Analysis & Purification System for Archaeological Water Bodies

*J.S.Kavathekar¹, Pavan Gaikwad², Akash Kafare³,
Pranit Kumbhar^{4*}*

*¹Assistant Professor, Department of Electronics and
Telecommunication Engineering, DACOE, Karad, India*

*^{2,3,4}Student, Department of Electronics and
Telecommunication Engineering, DACOE, Karad, India*

ABSTRACT

Clean and safe water is very important for everyone but many archaeological and rural water bodies do not have proper purification systems advanced methods like ro and uv are expensive and require continuous electricity which is not available in many remote areas because of this there is a need for a simple low-cost and eco-friendly solution. Our project Jalrakshak: real-time water analysis and purification system is designed to solve this problem in this system we use a four-stage natural filtration process using stones gravel activated carbon and sponge to remove dirt bad smell and impurities from water along with filtration we also monitor water quality in real time using sensors like turbidity temperature humidity and pH connected to raspberry pi zero w. An important feature of our system is the camera module the camera captures before and after images of the water purification process this gives clear visual proof of how the water quality improves after filtration it increases transparency and helps users authorities and conservation teams to clearly see the difference in water condition the images also help in maintaining records comparing results over time and building trust in the system the collected sensor data and images are sent to a mobile dashboard or telegram bot for remote monitoring the entire system works on solar power which makes it suitable for rural and heritage areas where electricity supply is limited Overall this project provides a simple affordable and sustainable solution for improving and monitoring water quality in archaeological water bodies.

Keywords:- *Water Purification, IoT Monitoring, Raspberry Pi, Natural Filtration, Solar Energy, Archaeological Water Bodies*

INTRODUCTION

Water is a basic need for all living beings. Many archaeological water bodies like ponds, wells, and temple tanks are very important for our history and culture. But nowadays, due to pollution, dirt, and lack of proper maintenance, the water in these places is becoming dirty and unsafe. In rural and heritage areas, there are no proper purification systems available.

Advanced systems like RO and UV are costly and need continuous electricity. These systems are not suitable for remote areas where electricity supply is not stable. Also, most traditional filtration systems do not provide real-time monitoring of water quality. Because of this, it becomes difficult to know whether the water is safe or not.

To solve this problem, we have developed JalRakshak – Real-Time Water Analysis and Purification System for Archaeological Water Bodies. In this project, we use a simple four stage natural filtration process using stones, gravel, activated carbon, and sponge to remove impurities from water. Along with purification, we also monitor water quality using sensors like turbidity, temperature, humidity, and pH.

We use Raspberry Pi Zero W to collect and process the sensor data. The data is sent to a mobile dashboard or Telegram bot so that water quality can be checked from anywhere. We have also added a camera module in our system. The camera captures before and after images of the water purification process. This helps to clearly see the improvement in water condition and provides visual proof of the purification process.

The entire system works on solar power, so it can operate even in areas where electricity is not available. Our main aim is to create a low-cost, eco-friendly, and

smart system that can help in improving and protecting archaeological water bodies.

LITERATURE SURVEY/REVIEW

While developing our project, we studied different research papers and existing water purification systems. We found that many modern purification methods like RO and UV are widely used for cleaning water. These systems are very effective in removing bacteria, viruses, and dissolved impurities. But they are expensive, require continuous electricity, and need regular maintenance. Because of this, they are not suitable for rural or archaeological areas where power supply and technical support are limited.

We also studied natural filtration methods. Many research studies show that using layers like stones, gravel, sand, and activated carbon is a simple and low-cost way to remove dirt and bad smell from water. Gravel removes large particles, sand removes smaller particles, and activated carbon helps in removing odor and some chemical impurities. These types of filters are easy to build and maintain, especially in rural areas.

We found that nowadays many projects use IoT technology for water quality monitoring. Sensors like turbidity sensor, pH sensor, and temperature sensor are connected to microcontrollers or Raspberry Pi to monitor water condition in real time. The data is sent to mobile apps or cloud platforms so that users can check water quality from anywhere.

This helps in detecting contamination quickly. Some projects also use solar energy to power water purification systems. Solar panels are useful in remote areas where electricity is not available. Solar-powered systems are eco-friendly and reduce operating costs.

However, from our study, we noticed that most systems focus either on purification or monitoring, but very few systems combine natural filtration, IoT monitoring, camera-based visual proof, and solar power in one system. Especially for archaeological water bodies, there is very limited work available.

So, based on this study, we decided to develop JalRakshak, which combines natural filtration, real-time monitoring, camera documentation, and renewable energy in a single low-cost system suitable for rural and heritage areas.

METHODOLOGY

1. First, we studied different water purification methods and selected a natural four-stage filtration process for our project.
2. We designed the filtration unit using four layers:
 - * Large stones to remove big particles
 - * Gravel and sand to remove small dirt particles
 - * Activated carbon to remove bad smell and some chemicals
 - * Sponge/foam to remove very fine impurities.
3. After building the filtration system, we selected sensors for water quality monitoring such as turbidity sensor, pH sensor, and DHT11/DHT22 sensor.
4. We connected all sensors to Raspberry Pi Zero W, which acts as the main controller of our system.
5. We wrote Python code to collect sensor data and process it in Raspberry Pi.
6. We connected the system to Wi-Fi and sent the data to a Telegram bot or online dashboard for real-time monitoring.
7. We integrated a camera module to capture before and after images of the water purification process.
8. The captured images and sensor data are stored and sent for remote monitoring.
9. We installed a solar panel and battery to power the entire system so that it can

work in remote areas without electricity.

10. Finally, we tested the complete system by checking filtration efficiency, sensor readings, image capturing, and data transmission.

CONTENT

The JalRakshak project is mainly focused on improving and monitoring the water quality of archaeological and rural water bodies. In many heritage places, water becomes dirty due to pollution and lack of maintenance. There are no proper systems to clean and monitor the water regularly. So, in this project, we have developed a simple and smart system that can purify water and also monitor its quality in real time.

In our system, we use a four-stage natural filtration process. First, water passes through large stones to remove big waste particles. Then it flows through gravel and sand to remove smaller dirt particles. After that, activated carbon is used to remove bad smell and some harmful impurities. Finally, a sponge layer is used to remove very fine particles.

This method is low cost and easy to maintain, especially in rural areas. For monitoring, we used sensors like turbidity sensor to check water clarity, pH sensor to measure acidity or alkalinity, and DHT sensor to measure temperature and humidity. All these sensors are connected to Raspberry Pi Zero W, which acts as the main controller.

The Raspberry Pi collects the data and sends it to a Telegram bot or online dashboard through Wi-Fi so that the water quality can be checked from anywhere. We have also added a camera module in our project. The camera captures images before and after the purification process. This helps us to clearly see the improvement in water condition and gives visual proof of the filtration process. It

also helps in keeping records for future comparison.

The entire system works on solar power with battery backup. This makes it suitable for remote areas where electricity

is not available. Overall, our project combines natural filtration, sensor monitoring, camera documentation, and renewable energy to create a simple, eco-friendly, and smart water purification system.

Table 1: Focus and Scope of JalRakshak Project

Focus	Scope
Water Purification	Natural four-stage filtration to purify water in ponds and heritage water boe-
Real-Time Monitoring	Monitoring water quality (turbidity, pH, temperature, humidity) with sensors
IoT Integration	Using Raspberry Pi and Wi-Fi to send water data to dashboard and Telegram bot
Renewable Energy	Using solar power to operate system in remote areas

Fig. 1: JalRakshak System Overview.

RESEARCH AND REVIEW

When we started planning this project, we first tried to understand the real condition of water bodies in rural and archaeological areas. We noticed that many old ponds, wells, and temple tanks are not cleaned regularly. Over time, dirt, waste, and environmental pollution reduce the water quality. In most cases, there is no proper system to check whether the water is safe or not. We studied different purification systems that are commonly used today.

In cities, people mostly use RO and UV purifiers. These systems are very effective but they are costly and depend completely on electricity. They also need proper servicing and technical support. In rural or heritage areas, such facilities are not easily available. Because of this, we understood that a simple and affordable solution is required for such places.

After that, we focused on basic filtration methods. We learned that using layers of natural materials can improve water quality to some extent. Big stones can stop large waste particles. Gravel and sand can reduce smaller dirt particles. Activated carbon can help in reducing bad smell and some unwanted substances. These materials are easily available and easy to replace. This type of filtration does not require complex setup, so we decided to use this concept in our system.

We also explored how technology can help in monitoring water condition. We understood that parameters like turbidity and pH give important information about water quality. By using sensors and connecting them to a small controller like Raspberry Pi, it is possible to read data continuously. With Wi-Fi connection, this data can be viewed on a mobile device. This idea helped us to include real-time monitoring in our project.

While thinking about improving transparency, we felt that only numerical data may not be enough. So we thought of adding a camera module. By capturing images before and after filtration, we can clearly see the difference in water condition. This also helps in maintaining records and building trust in the system.

Another important factor we considered was power supply. Since many archaeological sites do not have reliable electricity, we studied solar-powered systems. Solar panels with battery backup can run small electronic devices efficiently. This made us decide to power our system using solar energy so that it can work even in remote areas.

After reviewing all these points, we realized that most existing systems focus only on cleaning water or only on monitoring it. Very few solutions combine filtration, monitoring, visual proof, and renewable energy together. So we developed JalRakshak as a simple, practical, and complete system specially designed for rural and archaeological water bodies.

RESULT & DISCUSSION

After completing our JalRakshak system, we tested it by passing dirty water through the filtration unit. We observed that after passing through all four stages, the water became visibly clearer. In the first stage, large stones removed big waste particles. In the second stage, gravel and sand removed smaller dirt particles. Activated carbon helped in reducing bad smell, and the sponge layer removed fine impurities. Overall, the appearance of the water improved clearly after filtration. We also checked the sensor readings before and after filtration.

The turbidity sensor showed lower values after the water passed through the filter, which means the clarity improved. The pH sensor gave proper readings to show whether the water was acidic or alkaline. The temperature and humidity sensor also worked properly and displayed correct values. All the sensor data was successfully received by the Raspberry Pi Zero W. The system sent the data through Wi-Fi to the Telegram bot/dashboard. We were able to see real-time readings on our mobile phone.

The values were updated properly without much delay. This showed that the IoT part of our system was working correctly. The camera module captured images before and after purification. When we compared the images, we could clearly see the difference in water condition. This helped us to visually confirm the improvement and also maintain proper records. We also tested the solar power system. The solar panel charged the battery and powered the entire setup without any problem. This proved that our system can work in remote areas where electricity is not available. From our testing, we can say that the system worked successfully.

It improved water clarity, monitored important parameters, provided visual proof, and worked on renewable energy. However, for complete removal of bacteria and harmful microorganisms, additional methods like UV treatment may be added in future. Overall, our project achieved its main goal of developing a simple, low-cost, and smart system for water purification and monitoring.

CONCLUSION

In our project, we developed JalRakshak to improve and monitor the water quality of archaeological and rural water bodies. We used a simple four-stage natural filtration method to remove dirt and improve water clarity. Along with

filtration, we added sensors to check turbidity, pH, temperature, and humidity. The Raspberry Pi collected the data and sent it for real-time monitoring, which helped us to check water condition easily.

We also added a camera module to capture before and after images of the purification process. This helped us to clearly see the difference in water condition. The system works on solar power, so it can be used in remote areas where electricity is not available. Overall, our project successfully combined filtration, monitoring, and renewable energy in a simple and practical way.

FUTURE SCOPE

In future, our project can be improved by adding a UV or RO system so that bacteria and other harmful microorganisms can be removed completely. This will help to make the water safer for drinking. We can also add more sensors like TDS, dissolved oxygen, and conductivity sensors to get more accurate water quality readings. A separate mobile app can be developed for better monitoring and alerts.

The filtration unit can also be improved by adding an automatic cleaning system to reduce manual maintenance. In future, this system can be installed in bigger water bodies like lakes and large ponds. We can also improve the solar power system by using a bigger battery for longer backup. With more data collection, we can use AI or machine learning to predict water contamination and improve the system performance.

REFERENCES

1. WHO Water Treatment Overview <https://www.who.int/teams/environment-climate-change-and-health/water-sanitation-and-health>.
2. Slow Sand Filtration – Detailed Study <https://www.cawst.org/services/experts/technical-briefs>.

3. Activated Carbon in Water Treatment
<https://www.sciencedirect.com/topics/engineering/activated-carbon-water-treatment>.
4. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Smart-Water-Purification-Technique-Soni-Singh/9209283d4a194f6e09512bebd4e0b87097caec19>.
5. <https://www.sciencedirect.com>
(Search: Smart water monitoring using IoT).
6. <https://www.mdpi.com/journal/sensors>
7. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/IoT_Based_Water_Quality_Monitoring_System.
8. <https://thingspeak.com> (Cloud platform for IoT monitoring).
9. <https://www.jpl.nasa.gov/edu/resources/project/make-a-water-filter/>.
10. https://www.internationaljournalsrsg.org/uploads/specialissuepdf/ICIET_EM-2019/2019/CSE/3.AVL1115-go%20conference-CSE.pdf.